

BRIDGING MECHANISMS IN FIBRE-REINFORCED Ti MMCs

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SUMMARY: The physical nature of fibre bridging in a Tiβ21s/SCS-6 composite has been studied by using in-situ SEM observations under tension. Based on these in-situ SEM observations, a bridging model has been developed which includes effects of Poisson's ratio on interfacial shear stresses. Excellent agreement is found between predicted crack opening displacements (CODs) and in-situ SEM measurements. A method is then proposed to determine the interfacial shear stress by considering the average stress sustained by bridging fibres. The method also illustrates good agreement between predictions and experimental measurements reported in the open literature. Finally, crack closure at the crack tip and its possible effects on stress intensity factor range in the matrix of Ti MMCs are also addressed.

KEYWORDS: titanium-matrix composites, fibre-reinforced composites, silicon carbide, fibre bridging, in-situ SEM, crack opening displacement, modelling

INTRODUCTION

Fibre bridging is an important mechanism which leads to an increase of fatigue crack growth resistance in fibre-reinforced titanium matrix composites (Ti MMCs). Many models have been developed to predict effects of fibre bridging in fibre-reinforced metal or ceramic matrix composites [1-7]. One critical issue in modelling is the determination of bridging traction, $p(x)$, along the crack path. Currently, most models are based on a shear-lag strategy [1, 2, 5-7], and a knowledge of the value of interfacial shear stress, τ , is required in order to make predictions. Another set of models [3, 4] neglect details of load-transfer along the fibre-matrix interface, and assume that the applied stress is balanced by $p(x)$. These later models are simple to use, and the stress-balance assumption is "probably good enough" [8] when the unbridged crack is relatively long. However, under other circumstances, these stress-balance-models may overestimate effects of bridging. Therefore, the models based on shear-lag strategies are more flexible and can cope with a wider range of bridging geometries.

Obtaining $p(x)$ is only the first step to predict fatigue crack growth in Ti MMCs. To reach the final goal, another crack-tip-shielding factor F needs to be determined, so that the stress intensity factor range in the matrix, ΔK_m , can be calculated from equations such as $\Delta K_m =$

$F \cdot (\Delta K_a - \Delta K_b)$, where ΔK_a and ΔK_b are stress intensity factor ranges caused by the applied stress range and bridging traction range, respectively. Several forms of expression of F have been proposed [1, 2, 9], and they give values of $F \approx 0.5 \sim 1.0$.

Exact values of τ and F are difficult to obtain. It has been shown that crack growth simulations alone cannot determine uniquely the values of τ and F , even when experimental crack growth data exist for several stress ranges [10]. To solve the problem, precise measurements on crack opening displacements (CODs) are needed [8, 10]. The aim of this paper is therefore to investigate the bridging mechanisms in Ti MMCs by means of precise COD measurements and theoretical modelling. The physical nature of fibre bridging has also been examined by in-situ SEM observations under tension.

EXPERIMENTAL

The material used for in-situ SEM observations under tension is an 8-ply SCS-6 fibre reinforced Ti β 21s matrix composite (Ti β 21s/SCS-6) produced by Textron (USA) using a foil-fibre-foil procedure.

Single-edge-notch specimens of 4 mm wide and ~ 1.8 mm thick were tension-tension fatigued on a 100 kN Instron 1273 servo-hydraulic testing machine under load control at a load ratio ($R = \text{minimum load}/\text{maximum load}$) of 0.5 and at a frequency of 10 Hz. The initial notch length ranges from 0.4 to 1.0 mm. Fatigue tests were stopped after a crack extension of 1.3 \sim 1.5 mm had been obtained.

After fatigue the specimens were polished gently on one surface to reveal the first layer of fibres. Then the specimens were cut to 40 mm in length so that they could be loaded in a Hitachi S4000 FEG SEM, which has a secondary-electron-mode-resolution of $\sim 0.01 \mu\text{m}$. The loading of the stage was digitally controlled through a microcomputer. Interfacial sliding and opening were examined and COD profiles along the bridged cracks were measured.

PHYSICAL NATURE OF BRIDGING

Generally the development of fibre bridging involves the debonding of fibre-matrix interfaces ahead of the crack tip and the by-passing of the matrix crack around intact fibres with such debonded interfaces. This leaves intact fibres in the matrix crack wake to restrict the opening of the matrix crack. However, some controversy exists in certain basic aspects such as whether debonded fibre-matrix interfaces can still transfer load [3, 10]. It is important to clarify this because it directly affects the selection of equations to predict $p(x)$. If the debonded interfaces do not transfer load in Ti MMCs, then the bridging fibres will act as linear springs. As a result, COD should increase linearly with applied stress σ_a . On the other hand, if the debonded interfaces do still transfer load, the relationship between $p(x)$ and COD (or σ_a and COD) may not be linear and rather, it may approach a quadratic relationship [1].

The in-situ SEM observations and measurements under tension in this present study support the general picture of fibre bridging. However, some further details of fibre bridging have also been found. Within the interface-damaged-zone along bridging fibres, both interfacial sliding and opening are found when the composite is stressed along the longitudinal axis of the fibres (Fig.1). The existence of interfacial sliding suggest that the debonded interface can still

transfer load even at such surface positions, while the existence of interfacial opening suggests that the efficiency of transfer may not be as high as that predicted by shear-lag models (at least at surface locations).

Fig.1: Interfacial sliding and opening along a bridging fibre.

The load-transferring-capability of debonded interfaces is supported by COD measurements. Figure 2 shows the variation of half COD at two positions along a bridged crack. For comparison, the CODs under different σ_a are specified by the COD under the maximum σ_a at each corresponding position. As can be seen, the specific half COD increases non-linearly with σ_a at both positions. The degree of non-linearity is found to be higher at the position close to (0.01 mm behind) the crack tip than that at the position far away (1.3 mm) from the crack tip but close to the unbridged notch tip. The non-linear relationship between COD and σ_a indicates that the relationship between $p(x)$ and σ_a must also be non-linear. Thus other load-transferring mechanisms, such as sliding along the interface, must exist to create such non-linearity. It is expected that more efficient load-transfer by interfacial sliding will result in a higher degree of non-linearity between COD and σ_a .

Fig.2: Variation of specific half CODs with applied stress at different positions along crack path.

Therefore, the data in Fig.2 suggest that the debonded interface can still transfer load by sliding, and load-transfer by sliding is more efficient along fibres located close to crack tip than along those located far away from the crack tip but close to the unbridged notch tip.

The reasons for different load-transferring-efficiency along the crack path are complex. A Poisson's ratio effect may be one reason. It is expected [1-9] that $p(x)$ will be higher at positions close to the unbridged notch tip than at those close to the crack tip. Hence, the stress normal to the interface, and then the sliding stress along the interface, will be smaller at these former positions. Degradation of the interface by fatigue may be another reason [10,11], and the relaxation of matrix residual stress in the interfacial debonding zone could also be a factor. The interfacial debonding length is always longer at positions close to the unbridged notch tip, thus more matrix residual stress is expected to be released which will results in a decrease in

the stress normal to the debonded interface. In this paper, attention is paid to the influence of a Poisson's ratio effect.

MODELLING OF FIBRE BRIDGING

Figure 3 shows a schematic picture of a crack bridged by fibres in a composite subjected to a far-field stress, σ_a , in the direction of fibres. An interfacial debonding zone of length h is assumed. The interfacial shear stress, $\tau(x,y)$, is assumed to be related to the stress normal to the interface by Coulomb's law, i.e.,

$$\tau(x,y) = \tau_0 - \mu \cdot \sigma_p(x,y) \quad (1)$$

where τ_0 is the interfacial shear stress in the fibre direction at the position of $y = h$, μ is the coefficient of friction (which is found to be approximately 0.5 by comparing calculated and measured CODs), and $\sigma_p(x,y)$ is the stress normal to the interface caused by the Poisson's effect after σ_a is applied. It should be noted that both $\tau(x,y)$ and $\sigma_p(x,y)$ change not only along the crack path, but also along the debonding length of a single fibre. By making the same assumption as in [12] that the tangential strain at the interface is continuous, which is required to maintain contact between the fibre and the matrix, $\sigma_p(x,y)$ is related to the stresses in the fibre and matrix that locates within the interfacial sliding zone. For simplicity, a linear distribution of $\sigma_p(x,y)$ along axis y is assumed, and the average value of $\sigma_p(x,y)$ is used to give the average sliding stress along the fibre. Thus, $\tau(x,y)$ is approximated as $\tau(x)$

Fig.3: Schematic of fibre bridging in Ti MMCs.

$$\begin{aligned} \tau(x) &= \tau_0 \{1 - [B1 \cdot p(x) + B2 \cdot \sigma_c]\} \\ B1 &= \frac{\mu}{2D\tau_0} \cdot \frac{E_m}{E_f} \cdot v_f \cdot \frac{1}{V_f} \\ B2 &= \frac{\mu}{2D\tau_0} \cdot \frac{E_m}{E_c} \cdot (v_f - v_m) \\ D &= \frac{E_m}{E_f} (1 - v_f) + \frac{1 + V_f}{V_m} + v_m \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where σ_c is the stress in the composite at positions of $y \geq h$, E_m and E_f , V_m and V_f , and v_m and v_f are modulus, volume fraction, and Poisson's ratio of the matrix and the fibre, respectively. E_c is the composite modulus, and can be calculated by $E_c = E_f \cdot V_f + E_m \cdot V_m$. Thus, the unknown

parameter $\sigma_p(x,y)$ in Eq.(1) is substituted by another unknown parameter $p(x)$, but which can be solved numerically as follows.

With the method of Danchaivijit and Shetty [5] and using $\tau(x)$ as expressed in Eq.(2), the bridging traction $p(x)$ is obtained as

$$p(x) = \frac{\sigma_c}{2} \left\{ \frac{E_f \cdot V_f}{E_c} - \frac{E_m \cdot V_m}{E_c} \cdot (B1 \cdot \sigma_c) \cdot \frac{u(x)}{u_0(x)} + \sqrt{\left[\frac{E_f \cdot V_f}{E_c} - \frac{E_m \cdot V_m}{E_c} \cdot (B1 \cdot \sigma_c) \cdot \frac{u(x)}{u_0(x)} \right]^2 + \frac{4E_m V}{E_c} \cdot (1 - B2 \cdot \sigma_c) \cdot \frac{u(x)}{u_0(x)}} \right\} \quad (3)$$

where $u(x)$ is the half COD along crack path, and

$$u_0(x) = \frac{\sigma_c^2 \cdot E_m \cdot V_m \cdot \rho}{4E_c \cdot E_f \cdot V_f^2 \cdot \tau_0}, \quad (4)$$

where ρ is the fibre radius. Self-consistent $u(x)$ and $p(x)$ can be obtained by solving Eqs.(3) and (5) numerically and simultaneously

$$u(x) = \frac{4}{E'} \int_x^a \left\{ \int_0^{a'} G(x', a', W) \cdot [\sigma_a(x') - p(x')] \cdot dx' \right\} \cdot G(x, a', W) \cdot da' \quad (5)$$

where E' is the modulus of an orthotropic material containing a crack normal to the loading direction, and $G(x,a,W)$ is an appropriate weight function. The expression of E' and $G(x,a,W)$ can be found in [13].

Equation (3) is a general expression of $p(x)$ - $u(x)$ relationship. If the effects of Poisson's ratio are neglected, i.e., $\tau(x) = \tau_0$, then Eq.(3) will be simplified to the form which is exactly the same as that found elsewhere [5]. If it is further assumed that $p(x) = \sigma_c = \sigma_a$, then Eq.(3) will further be the same as that given in other work [1].

PREDICTED $u(x)$ and $\tau(x)$

Figure 4 shows the excellent agreement in CODs in one specimen under different σ_a between the in-situ measurements and predictions made by the model in this present paper by using interfacial shear stress as a curve-fitting parameter. As can be seen in Eqs. (2) and (3) the variation of $\tau(x)$ due to the Poisson's ratio effect has been incorporated in Eq. (3) through $p(x)$ and σ_c . Therefore, in practice, it is necessary only to use τ_0 as a COD-curve-fitting parameter because $\tau(x)$ is determined once τ_0 is given.

The distributions of $\tau(x)$ used to obtain best-fitting CODs under different σ_a in Fig.4 are shown in Fig.5. An important feature of the distributions is that even for an identical bridged crack in a given specimen geometry, $\tau(x)$ varies not only along the crack path, but also with σ_a . Under a given σ_a , $\tau(x)$ decreases gradually as the position x moves away from the crack tip to the unbridged notch tip. The amount of decrease in $\tau(x)$ is larger when σ_a is higher. This

is reasonable because the Poisson's ratio effect will be higher when the longitudinal stress is higher. The implication of the variation of $\tau(x)$ with σ_a even for the same crack is important in understanding bridging mechanisms. It seems that when σ_a is lower than the maximum σ_a during a cycle of loading-unloading, τ_0 , which is the interfacial shear stress at the end of interfacial sliding zone, acts to describe an on-off stick-slip situation. A lower σ_a results in a lower $p(x)$, which needs a lower τ_0 to transfer load through the interface. Combining with the Poisson's ratio effect, $\tau(x)$ will decrease with σ_a . Therefore, it seems that it is the bridging traction needed under a given σ_a that actually determines $\tau(x)$.

Fig.4: Measured and calculated half CODs for a specimen under different σ_a .

Fig.5: Distribution of $\tau(x)$ used to obtain the calculated half CODs in Fig.4.

Since $\tau(x)$ depends on so many factors, it is unlikely that a direct relationship between $\tau(x)$ and other parameters such as specimen geometry and σ_a can be obtained. Thus in this present paper, an indirect method has been proposed to determine $\tau(x)$.

A METHOD TO DETERMINE $\tau(x)$ UNDER OTHER LOADING CONDITIONS

Instead of considering $\tau(x)$ directly, an average bridging traction, P (defined as the average stress sustained by bridging fibres), is calculated and compared with the average stress C sustained by bridging fibres based on a stress-balance strategy (such as the Ghosn model [4]). The results show in Fig.6 indicate an excellent linear relationship between P and C , i.e.,

$$C = \kappa P \quad (6)$$

where κ is 1.06 for 4-mm-wide specimens with a notch with unbridged length from 0.4 to 1.0 mm. Since C is simply a function of known parameters of specimen geometry, loading configuration, and σ_a , Eq.(6) can therefore be used as a criterion to determine P and $p(x)$. The procedure is just to numerically calculate $p(x)$ from Eqs. (3) to (5) by assuming different τ_0 values until Eq.(6) is satisfied. With this method, the difficulty in determining $\tau(x)$ is bypassed, and to predict bridging effects needs only specimen geometry, σ_a , and material constants such as modulus and Poisson's ratio of fibre and matrix, fibre volume fraction, and fibre radius. The predicted $u(x)$ obtained from this method agrees very well with experimental data [4] for 5-mm-wide Ti MMC specimens (Fig.7).

It should be noted that $\kappa=1.06$ may be valid only for specimens with width of approximately 4 mm. This is because the crack growth may not be steady in such narrow specimens. As a result, the bridging traction cannot balance the applied stress. Part of the applied stress is transferred to the matrix ahead of crack. Therefore, P is found to be slightly smaller than C . With an increase in specimen width, P is expected to be closer to C . Our further COD measurements suggest that κ approaches unity in 10-mm-wide specimens.

Fig.6: A linear relationship between P and C in 4-mm-wide specimens.

The distributions of $p(x)$ have also been predicted and compared with predictions [14] made by another method, which includes the determination of the three coefficients in an assumed $p(x)$ - x relationship of $p(x)$ with the assistance of experimental COD data. Since the centre-notched specimens used [14] are 19 mm in width, $\kappa=1.0$ has been used. As can be seen in Fig.8, good agreement is also found between the two predictions.

Fig.7: Comparison of $u(x)$ calculated by the current model by using Eq.(6) as a criterion with that measured by Ghosn [4].

Fig.8: Comparison of $p(x)$ along crack path predicted by this present model and by Buchanan et al. [14].

The above examples show that the method proposed in this present paper to predict bridging effects in Ti MMCs works well for a wide range of specimen geometries and applied stresses. The interfacial shear stress, although it must be used in the calculation, is not needed *a priori*. In addition, with the assistance of accurate COD measurements, the mechanisms of variation of $\tau(x)$ with σ_a and crack extension can be deduced from the model.

CRACK CLOSURE EFFECTS

The in-situ observations and local strain measurements suggest that crack closure may occur in Ti MMCs when the load ratio R is low. Figure 9 shows that the crack tip opens up gradually as σ_a increases. Local strain measurements (Fig. 10) also show that the load-strain curve deviates slightly (as indicated by the arrow in the figure) as the applied load approaches the minimum load for the case of $R=0.1$. The deviation is believed to be a result of crack closure, since it is not found when $R=0.5$ for the same specimen.

Fig.9: Gradual open of crack tip in a Ti MMC specimen.

Fig.10: Local load-strain relationship across a bridged crack.

The existence of crack closure at low R may demand that the relationship of $\Delta K_m = F \cdot (\Delta K_a - \Delta K_b)$ be modified by adding closure effects. Hence, care should also be taken when trying to deduce parameters governing bridging laws from fatigue crack growth data, especially when low R ratios are employed to conduct the fatigue tests.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Debonded interfaces can transfer load even at surface locations. The interfacial opening along bridging fibres observed at surface positions decreases the efficiency of load transfer through interface.
2. The predictions made by a model proposed to include effects of Poisson's ratio agree well with in-situ measurements. The model also indicates that during a cycle of loading-unloading the interfacial shear stress varies even for the same bridged crack. It appears that it is the bridging traction needed to satisfy the relationship $C = \kappa \cdot P$ under a given applied stress that determines the interfacial stress.
3. A linear relationship is found between the average bridging traction predicted by the model in this present paper and that predicted by the model based on a stress-balance strategy. Using this linear relationship, the only parameters needed to predict fibre bridging effects in Ti MMCs are materials constants, specimen geometry descriptions, and the applied stress range.

4. Crack closure effects may need to be considered when predicting effective stress intensity factor ranges in the matrix of Ti MMCs.

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